

Memory

Adrià
Serarols Llorens
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Energy Engineering

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Summary

There is a compelling need of encouraging energy efficiency in buildings, enhancing green technologies and promoting advanced thermal energy storage solutions. TESSE2B will enable the optimal use of renewable energy and provide one of the most advantageous solutions for correcting the mismatch that often occurs between the supply and demand of energy in residential buildings.

The target of TESSE2B is to design, develop, validate and demonstrate a modular and low cost thermal storage technology based on solar collectors and highly efficient heat pumps for heating, cooling and DHW production. The idea is to develop advanced compact integrated PCM TES tanks exploiting RES (solar and geothermal) in an efficient manner coupled with enhanced PCM BHEs that will take advantage of the increased underground thermal storage and maximize the efficiency of the GCHP.

The two TES tanks developed within TESSE2B project integrate different PCM materials: enhanced paraffin PCM and salt- hydrates PCM. In both of them a highly efficient heat exchanger will be included. Although the concept of phase change thermal storage has been demonstrated, TESSE2B project discriminates itself through incorporating: PCM materials innovation, advanced energy management through self-learning model-based control system, enhanced PCM BHEs and compact modular design of thermal storage tank.

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Preface

As many people may know, the current energy system (and how it is going to evolve for the next decades) probably may be the most important issue to be considered, regarding the whole world. It is essential to know what is the current situation, and which are the current trends, to be able to face these circumstances in the near future responding properly.

There is a simple statement which is interesting to outline: “Power is Power”. We are living in an era where every one of our necessities require energy, no matter if it’s a basic thing, or not. Having a deficit of energy means decreasing quality life. That’s why having access to energy should be a human right for everyone. But then, some questions arise: how is it possible to provide energy to everyone? Are we doing it properly? Are there enough resources for everyone in the world?

Some decades ago, the concept of renewable energy was born, and nowadays there are different types of renewable energy systems that are becoming quite popular, and they produce energy using natural sources such as wind, solar radiation or the strength of water, for example.

Although these technologies require quite high investments to build new installations, once they start producing energy, the cost of generation it’s nearly 0, as the fuel is completely free, so in a couple of years the initial investment becomes totally covered, making it a more profitable solution in long term than conventional methods, by the time that no greenhouse gases are emitted while obtaining energy, making it a more sustainable alternative.

During the last years, european countries who are willing to become less dependant on conventional energy sources started developing many pioneer research projects to make the technology evolve. Horizon 2020 is the financial instrument implementing the Innovation Union, a Europe 2020 flagship initiative aimed at securing Europe’s global competitiveness.

Seen as a means to drive economic growth and create jobs, Horizon 2020 has the political backing of Europe’s leaders and the Members of the European Parliament. They agreed that research is an investment in our future and so put it at the heart of the EU’s blueprint for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth and jobs.

By coupling research and innovation, Horizon 2020 is helping to achieve this with its emphasis on excellent science, industrial leadership and tackling societal challenges. The goal is to ensure Europe produces world-class science, removes barriers to innovation and makes it easier for the public and private sectors to work together in delivering innovation. In particular, one of the main objectives is to achieve a 20 % of the energy consumed to be generated from renewable sources, at 2020 by every country within the EU.

As Obama said back in 2010, “*the nation that leads the clean energy economy will be the nation that leads the global economy*”.

I. TESSE²B project

I.I. Description

The energy use in buildings has been estimated to be approximately 40% of the EU total energy consumption. The Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) requires that all new buildings will have nearly zero-energy demand by the end of 2020, indicating that the majority of the energy that these buildings would require would come from renewable energy sources (RES). Currently RES in buildings for domestic heating and hot water production is still limited with a proportion under 1%. Due to this fact, there is a need of encouraging energy efficiency in buildings, enhance green technologies and promote advanced thermal storage solutions, in a way to reduce energy consumption and minimize CO₂ emissions.

TESSE²B is a low cost thermal storage technology based on solar collectors and efficient heat pumps for heating, cooling and domestic hot water (DHW) production, financed by the EC as part of its H2020 program. It enables the optimal use of renewable energy and provides corrective measures against the mismatch that often occurs between the supply and demand of energy in residential buildings.

It is an integrated package with thermal storage technology (Thermal Energy Storage tanks - TES tanks), using solar collectors, geothermal energy, thermal accumulation and highly efficient heat pumps. The TES tanks developed within TESSE²B project are integrated with different Phase Change Materials (PCMs). In both, a highly efficient heat exchanger is included. It is also coupled with PCM borehole heat exchangers (BHEs). These will take advantage of the underground thermal storage and maximize the efficiency of the ground heat pumps (GCHP).

The success of TESSE²B solution is based on an interdisciplinary approach combining innovations on different levels:

- » Nano-enhancement of paraffin PCM (NEPCM).
- » Smart self-learning control algorithm.
- » Enhancement of BHES by integration of PCM into the grout.
- » Development of a protective and economically feasible coating for the HE, in case of the salt hydrates PCM.
- » Stackable modular design of TES tanks (including the immersed HE).

The consortium consists of ten partners from eight different European countries:

- » **IPS** coordinates the project.
- » **CRES** is the Greek national center for renewable energy sources, including geothermal and solar thermal, rational use of energy and energy saving.
- » **TEISTE** represents the Mechanical Engineering Department of Technologiko Ekpedeftiko Idrimastereas Elladas which is a higher education institute.
- » **GEOTEAM** is a company with project experience in the exploration, development and monitoring of portable mineral water resources and geothermal energy.
- » **UOI** represents the laboratory of thin solid films (TSF Lab) of the Department of Physics at University of Ioannina.
- » **SGGW** is a research and technological institution focusing on the practical application of renewable energy sources and technologies in buildings and small-scale installations and their modelling and control remote via internet.
- » **RUB** is a research and technological institution which represents the Power Systems technology and Power Mechatronics (EneSys) of University of Bohum.
- » **ECOSERVEIS** is a non-profit Organization working on promotion and education on energy, energy efficiency and renewable energies.
- » **PCM PRODUCTS** is a company active in the development of Phase Change Materials and related applications.
- » **Z&X** is a company with successful activity in the field of mechanical installations and in Renewable Energy, meaning geothermal, photovoltaic and solar thermal systems.

1.2. Objectives

The Spanish TESSE²B demo site is located in a small town 100km far from Barcelona called Calonge de Segarra. With 202 citizens, 37 km² of surface and 643m of altitude, Calonge de Segarra has a Continental - Mediterranean climate due to its relative altitude of 600 to 780 meters. It is characterized by quite cold winters, with an average of 3 °C in February, minimums between -2 and -10 °C, with a lot of fog, temperatures often below 0 °C, frost and some snowfall. The summers are warm, with an average of 21 °C in July, with maximums up to 35 °C.

The precipitations are irregular, mainly occurring in autumn and spring, the summer being the driest season. The average annual precipitation is about 500 mm. In winter, precipitation is usually in form of snow.

The technological objectives of the whole project can be listed as follows:

- » Selection and characterization of candidate PCM to ensure optimum design and performance for high efficiency PCM TES tanks and enhanced PCM borehole heat exchangers.
- » Exploit nanotechnology to develop a new nano-composite enhanced paraffin PCM (NEPCM).
- » Development of a protective thin film coating against corrosivity of salt-hydrates to the heat exchanger (HE).
- » Design, optimization and development of the compact modular TES tanks including a high performance HE.
- » Development of a smart model-based control system for efficient TESSE²B operation and integration into robust working prototype.
- » Demonstration, on-site monitoring and technology validation of prototypes of a single building in three pilot sites.
- » Cost-effectiveness analysis of TESSE²B solution to evaluate the return-on-investment period.
- » Design an effective exploitation strategy and business plan to demonstrate the overall benefits in the several levels of the TESSE²B solution.

I. TESSE²B project

I.2. Objectives

In this particular report and during the last months, the scope focused on giving support during the development of the project and its ongoing tasks, as well as making parallel studies in order to verify that the calculations already made in the previous states of the project are correct, and also for self learning purposes. The studies and analysis made are listed below:

Analysis of the energy demand of the case study

Performing a model of the given house and taking into account the meteorological data from the site, to develop a demand profile for heating, cooling, and domestic hot water needs. This energy demand estimation will be used to properly size the renewable energy technologies, as well as the energy storage system.

Sizing of the whole installation

- » Calculate the needed power of the Heat Pump, which is found according to the heat and cooling demands of the house.
- » Sizing of the Borehole Heat Exchangers, which will determine how many wells will have to be drilled, and its depth.
- » Solar Collectors surface, to cover 30% of the Heating + Domestic Hot Water demand, and estimate its energy production.

Sizing of the thermal energy storage system

This part will compare the conventional hot water tank versus the use of the TESSE²B solution, which includes phase change materials, as they are an innovative option which can reduce not only losses but also the size of the tank.

Economic and environmental analysis

Finally, an economic and environmental analysis of the project will determine if Tesse²B solution is attractive for customers, which is the approximate investment required to develop the solution, and which is the payback period, in comparison with other heating storage systems available.

2. Demosite Description

2.1. Geographical characteristics

The house where the project takes place is called “Casa del Mestre”, located in **Calonge de Segarra** municipality. The house is isolated from the rest of the village, and there is just an old church nearby, being both buildings surrounded by fields. The house will be used by a single family, which is estimated to be 4 people. The external walls are made of stone, but the inside has been renovated recently to improve its isolation. The following tables display the basic information regarding the site and its characteristics:

Province	Barcelona	Year of construction	1800
Region	Anoia	Habitable surface	150 m ²
Municipality / Village	Calonge de Segarra	Energy qualification	F
UTM Coordinates	X: 373.803 Y: 4.642.681	Type of building	Isolated single-family house
Altitude	613 meters	Climate Zone	C2

Tables 2.1.1. and 2.1.2. Geographical data

Image 2.1.1. Demosite's dwelling

2.2. Geological characteristics

From a geological point of view, the demosite is located in the north-eastern sector of the Ebre basin, part of what is known as the Catalan Central Depression. The so-called “Conca” or Depression of the Ebre corresponds to the pre-Pyrenean basin of the Pyrenees and constitutes a morphostructural unit of the Iberian Peninsula. It is a sedimentary basin of tertiary age (oligo-myocene) mainly drained by the Ebre river. It has the shape of a triangle and is bounded by the Pyrenees to the north, to the Iberian Chain at south, and to the Coastal Catalan Chain, to the South-East.

So, there are three areas of contribution with their respective alluvial depositional systems that converge approximately in the lake area of Mequinensa. The base of the basin on which the tertiary clay sediments accumulate is formed by materials from Triassic, Jurassic and occasionally from the Cretaceous, except in the eastern part where it is based on the top of a Paleozoic substratum.

The terrain has been analyzed and several types of material have been recognized. Initially from the surface of the terrain and up to 12 m depth (thickness of 12 m) there's a level of brown Sandstone (level A). At depth (12 m) and up to 46 m, brown Argilites were found (level B) with a detected thickness of 34 m. Between 46 and 59 meters in depth (13 m in thickness), gray Marl (level C) has been found. Below this level and until the end of the drilling (from 59 m to 90 / 94 m), there is a mix between light gray Gypsum and Marl (level D) (31 to 34 m thickness).

The following table (2.2.1) is a recap of the materials found and their respective thickness:

Level	Material	Depth (m)	Thickness (m)
R	Anthropic Filler	0 to 0,5 / 1,5	0,5 - 1,5
A	Brown Sandstone	0,5 / 1,5 to 12	12
B	Brown Argilites	12 to 46	34
C	Gray Marl	46 to 59	13
D	Light gray Gypsum and Marl	59 to 90 / 94	31 - 34

Table 2.2.1. Description of the soil's materials

2. Demosite Description

2.2. Geological characteristics

Figure 2.2.1. Soil scheme

This image (Figure 2.2.1) represents the table described on the previous page. The four material levels are displayed. This image is comes from the thermal response test report, carried out by Quali to determine the soil's thermal conductivity.

When speaking about the underground water and according to the Catalan Water Agency (ACA), the area where the house is located corresponds to a sector formed by the groundwater mass "Mesozoic and Tertiary Area of Gaia-Anoia".

This water mass occupies approximately the pre-coastal block of the Gaia, including the marginal paleogene of the central depression (Carme-Igualada). In fact, in this sector, the paleogene covers the mesozoic layer extensively, giving rise to a structure of smooth folds, in which alternate the permeable and impermeable levels, so it is difficult

to separate hydrogeologically both parts. Among its problematic limits it is necessary to indicate that to the northeast there is the Paleozoic of Capellades, to the south it is separated from the Bonastre block by the Jurassic strip of the Montmell, and towards the southwest it is separated from Miramar by the straits of Cabra del Camp. There are numerous type of rocks: paleogene limestone, mesozoic limestone, paleogene conglomerate, paleogene detritus materials, triassic marls and plaster, paleozoic materials and granites, and quaternary deposits.

A level of underground water has been detected at 58 m deep. This level is associated to the contact between the materials of levels C and D. It can be spotted on the image above as a blue line (see Figure 2.2.1).

2.3. Building characteristics

The building consists of a two floor single-family dwelling. This means that it is not attached to any other building, by means that it may require a higher energy demand in terms of heating and cooling, if the external walls are not properly isolated. Speaking about the walls, they are constituted by 45 cm of stone, 3 cm of polyurethane, and 2 cm of plaster, being therefore 50 cm thick in total. Windows are all double glazed with wooden frame.

The conductivity of the walls and windows has been estimated according to their thickness and materials (the values used in the calculations are showed on the table below).

The house was renovated some years ago in purpose of the TESSe2B project. The renovation included all the new windows and improved the walls isolation. The heating system of the house will

consist on a heat pump with inverter, to be able to provide heat and cool, combined with borehole heat exchangers, so the COP of the heat pump improves significantly, and therefore more renewable energy its being used. Finally, solar thermal panels will be installed on the rooftop to cover part of the domestic hot water needs and heat demand.

All the renewable technologies will be able to store energy when needed in a thermal energy storage system, which is discussed later on in this report (see chapter 7).

As said, all technologies are installed right next to the house or at its rooftop, so the transportation heat losses become minimal. Floor and elevation schemes can be found in the next page, and also the hydraulic scheme which includes the storage tanks.

Name	Conductivity (W/m ² ·K)	Surface (m ²)
North Walls	2,94	51,479
South Walls	2,94	41,815
East Walls	2,94	56,963
West Walls	2,94	58,648
Windows	4,83	11,764

Table 2.3.1. Walls and windows characteristics

Figures 2.3.1 and 2.3.2.
Architectural structure of the house

Figure 2.3.3. TESSe2B Hydraulic scheme

The house has three bedrooms and a bathroom on the upper floor, and the kitchen, living room, and second bathroom on the ground floor. The bedrooms and living room are south oriented, to provide as much natural light as possible in most used spaces.

As it can be seen on Figure 2.3.3 above, there are different circuits that make up the whole hydraulic system. On the left side, there are the **borehole heat exchangers**, which connect with the heat pump. As it is supposed to have inverter technology, it will be able to provide either heating and cooling, to be consumed directly, or stored in the tanks.

At the top, there are the **solar thermal panels**, which can provide heat directly, or store it in the tank for later use. These panels will be installed at the rooftop, south oriented, using a metal structure to provide the appropriate orientation and angle to the panels.

There are different tanks to store the energy when needed, which contain **Phase Change Materials (PCM)**, for both heating and cooling. Needless to say, the tanks are connected to the house to provide either heat or cool when the renewable sources are not enough to cover the energy demand.

All the elements will be controlled using an algorithm, as the system has many operating possibilities. This control algorithm will define where the energy has to be transferred at any time, and the system will behave according to weather predictions, also taking into account the variability on electricity price, to optimize the production and store energy when the prices become lower and use the storage system when these are higher, always assuring that the demand is always covered.

To do so, temperature sensors and flowmeters have to be placed within the circuit, to monitor the heat or cooling capacity of the tanks, and control the energy production in real time. This supposes a complete new hydraulic system, so the old installations must be substituted by new components and pipes.

All the calculations for the sizing of the different components can be found later on in the report.

3. Household Energy Demand Calculation

3.1. Terrain Modeling

Before calculating the building's energy demand, or sizing any of the renewable technologies, it is important to take a close look into the weather conditions at the demosite. Not just the outside temperature, but also the ground temperature at different depths, as it influences directly the size of the Borehole Heat Exchangers, and the overall performance of the Heat Pump.

To do so, hourly data was gathered during a whole year, using a small weather station installed on the demosite, to obtain information about temperature, humidity, wind, and solar radiation. This information is also complemented with the use of weather data from IDAE, AEMET and INE (see references [15], [21], [25]).

On the other hand, the geological data (see chapter 2.2) allowed to estimate values such as the conductivity and heat capacity per cubic meter of the soil.

With all this information, a **Thermal model of the Soil** has been developed, which estimates the ground temperatures at different depths and for every day of the year. An overview of the results can be seen on the next graph:

Figure 3.1.1. Evolution of the soil temperature

Figure 3.1.1 on the previous page gives us a lot of information about the soil conditions and behaviour along the year. Firstly, it is noticeable how the temperature becomes stable at 20 m depth, where it is not affected by weather nor season. The temperature at which it stabilizes is found to be approximately 15,7 °C.

Another interesting point is the fact that the soil experiences **thermal inertia** from month to month. For example, when looking at the temperature curve drawn by December, it can be seen that, despite the surface temperature is relatively low, when going down a few meters, the temperature increases, even above the ones from July or August and, afterwards, it stabilizes. This phenomena is due to the fact that the ground retains the heat, and does not evacuate it as easily as the air, creating this type of temperature curves, in which one month always depends on the previous ones, and affects the following ones.

Next graphs display the different air temperature profiles that occur at the demosite, split into different ranges, versus the hours of occurrence on the other axis. This gives a quick outlook to understand the temperature conditions which happen more often, as well as which are the coldest and warmest temperatures reached on site.

As it can be seen, the lowest and highest temperatures reached are -1 and 31 °C, respectively. Most of the year, temperatures happen to be between 8 and 24 °C. On account on that, we can predict that the sizing will be more focused on the heating side than on cooling.

Figures 3.1.2. Temperature bins of the demosite

3. Household Energy Demand Calculation

3.2. Housing Modeling

This section consists in the estimation of the domestic hot water needs of the case study. The heating and cooling demand of the dwelling are calculated later in the report (see chapter 4, Selection of the Heat Pump).

Domestic Hot Water (DHW)

The first reference values have been obtained from *Código Técnico, Sección HE4 [3]*, where it estimates a water consumption of 30 liters · person/day, at 60 °C. This value had to be corrected, as the temperature that has been estimated for the water to be the demanded is 45 °C. The corrections have been made for every month taking into consideration the temperature in which the water arrives to the house through its pipes, which has been estimated to be the ground temperature at 1 meter depth. To do so, the following equation has been used [3].

$$D(T) = \sum_1^{12} D_i(T)$$

$$D_i(T) = D_i(60\text{ °C}) \times \left(\frac{60 - T_i}{T - T_i} \right)$$

Where,

D(T)	is the total annual DHW demand at the desired temperature (T);
D _i (T)	is the monthly _i equivalent DHW demand at the desired temperature (T);
D _i (60 °C)	is the monthly _i DHW demand at 60 °C;
T	is the desired temperature of the water (45 °C);
T _i	is the mean temperature for the cold water in month

The calculations, assuming that there will be 4 people living in the house, give us a daily profile, for every month of the year. Note that the temperature T_i has been estimated to be the soil temperature at 1 meter depth as a reference. The total demand (liters) for four persons in a day, for every month, is shown in the next Table 3.2.1.

	Jan.	Feb.	March	April	May	June	July	August	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
T _i (°C)	10,65	7,69	6,8	8,19	11,15	16,12	20,47	23,65	24,62	23,2	19,7	15,24
DHW (l/day)	172,40	168,24	167,12	168,89	173,17	182,32	193,37	204,30	208,32	202,56	191,15	180,48

Table 3.2.1. Daily Domestic Hot Water demand and water inlet temperature (soil's temperature)

After that, the DHW demand for a day has been split into the different hours of the day, for every month, to obtain a reasonably realistic hourly profile for every month, in liters. The estimated values appear on the following table:

Hour	January	Feb.	March	April	May	June	July	August	Sept.	October	Nov.	Dec.
0:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6:00	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	6	6	6	5	5
7:00	35	34	34	34	36	40	42	43	43	43	41	38
8:00	25	24	24	24	25	25	17	28	28	28	27	25
9:00	10	10	10	10	10	10	11	12	12	12	11	10
10:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
12:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
13:00	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	6	6	6	5	5
14:00	12	12	12	12	12	12	13	14	15	14	13	12
15:00	10	10	10	10	10	12	13	14	15	14	13	12
16:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
17:00	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
18:00	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	6	5	5	5
19:00	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	12	12	11	10	10
20:00	15	14	14	14	15	16	17	17	17	17	17	16
21:00	25	24	24	24	25	27	30	30	30	30	29	27
22:00	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	10	10	10	8	8
23:00	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Total	172,40	168,24	167,12	168,89	173,17	182,32	193,37	204,30	208,32	202,56	191,15	180,48

Table 3.2.2. Hourly Domestic Hot Water Demand (liters)

The criteria to estimate the consumption has been similar for every month. At the morning people are supposed to take a shower, and apart from that, the water consumption is concentrated during the cooking times and in other hours where the people might be at home and need hot water eventually.

Finally, this consumption has been translated into energy demand, which is the energy needed to heat the water from the initial cold temperature T_i , up until 45 °C. This energy can be provided both by the Solar Thermal panels, the Heat Pump, or the thermal storage system.

3. Household Energy Demand Calculation

3.2. Housing Modeling

The calculations used to determine the energy requirements for domestic hot water are based on the specific heat formula: $Q = m \cdot C \cdot \Delta T$

where,

Q	is the energy needed to heat the water mass up to 45 °C
m	is the water mass to be heated (kg)
C	is the specific heat of the fluid (for water, C = 4,181)
ΔT	is the temperature difference between 45 °C and the initial temperature, T_i

Hour	Jan.	Feb.	March	April	May	June	July	August	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
0:00	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
1:00	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
2:00	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
3:00	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
4:00	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
5:00	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
6:00	0,199	0,216	0,221	0,213	0,196	0,167	0,142	0,148	0,142	0,151	0,146	0,172
7:00	1,396	1,473	1,508	1,453	1,415	1,341	1,196	1,066	1,017	1,088	1,204	1,313
8:00	0,997	1,039	1,064	1,026	0,982	0,838	0,769	0,694	0,662	0,708	0,793	0,864
9:00	0,398	0,433	0,443	0,427	0,393	0,335	0,313	0,297	0,284	0,303	0,323	0,345
10:00	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
11:00	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
12:00	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
13:00	0,199	0,216	0,221	0,213	0,196	0,167	0,142	0,148	0,165	0,151	0,146	0,172
14:00	0,478	0,519	0,532	0,513	0,471	0,402	0,370	0,347	0,355	0,354	0,381	0,414
15:00	0,398	0,433	0,443	0,427	0,393	0,402	0,370	0,347	0,355	0,354	0,381	0,414
16:00	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
17:00	0,199	0,216	0,221	0,213	0,196	0,167	0,142	0,123	0,118	0,126	0,146	0,172
18:00	0,199	0,216	0,221	0,213	0,196	0,167	0,142	0,123	0,142	0,126	0,146	0,172
19:00	0,398	0,433	0,443	0,427	0,393	0,335	0,284	0,297	0,284	0,278	0,293	0,345
20:00	0,598	0,606	0,621	0,598	0,589	0,536	0,484	0,421	0,402	0,430	0,499	0,553
21:00	0,997	1,039	1,064	1,026	0,982	0,905	0,854	0,743	0,710	0,759	0,852	0,933
22:00	0,319	0,346	0,354	0,342	0,314	0,268	0,227	0,247	0,236	0,253	0,235	0,276
23:00	0,079	0,086	0,044	0,085	0,078	0,067	0,056	0,049	0,047	0,050	0,058	0,069
Total month	212,71	203,83	229,67	215,46	210,83	183,13	170,44	156,80	147,69	159,32	168,36	192,86

Table 3.2.3. Hourly Domestic Hot Water Demand (kWh)

The total energy needed for the whole year is about 2251,16 kWh.

Figure 3.2.4. Monthly Domestic Hot Water Demand (kWh)

The graph above (3.2.4) is a representation of the table seen on the previous page, to provide a more visual overview of the energy related to the Domestic Hot Water needs.

As it can be seen, the **energy demand** happens to be **higher in winter and lower in summer**. This phenomena might not be obvious at first sight. When looking at the demand in terms of liters, we can see that it becomes higher in summer (see Table 3.2.1), which is fairly reasonable, as we all tend to use more water (take more showers, for example), when the weather is hotter. However, in terms of energy demand, the trend seems to be the opposite. This is due to the fact that the water arrives to the house in lower temperature during winter, and therefore the gap between this temperature and the desired temperature is wider, requiring more energy to reach the final temperature, whereas in summer, the cold temperature of the water is not as cold as in winter, so the energy required to reach the final temperature is significantly lower, as it can be seen on the graph.

4. Selection of the Heat Pump

To calculate the heating and cooling needs of the dwelling, all the possible heat losses and gains occurring inside the house have to be taken into consideration in order to develop a proper simulation. The following calculations estimate the peak power needed for heating and cooling, so the Heat Pump model can be selected according to the power needed. The comfort temperatures and humidity levels considered in the calculations are:

	Temperature (°C)	Humidity (%)
Winter	20	50
Summer	24	50

Table 4.1. Comfort conditions

Overall, it is needed to calculate a balance between all the heat sources and losses, which the heat pump will have to compensate to guarantee the comfort levels seen in Table 4.1 at all time inside the house. Losses from the walls, windows, air infiltrations (sensible and latent heat), heat losses coming from the use of electronic devices and heat generated by people living inside the house are taken into consideration into the balance. No heat associated with lighting sources has been considered, as all the original lighting system has been substituted by LED.

The formulas used to calculate the different heat sources and the results appear below:

$$Q_{\text{walls}} = S_{\text{walls}} \cdot U_{\text{walls}} \cdot \Delta T$$

$$Q_{\text{windows}} = S_{\text{windows}} \cdot U_{\text{windows}} \cdot \Delta T$$

$$Q_{\text{people}} = N_{\text{people}} \cdot F_{\text{people}}$$

$$Q_{\text{devices}} = \text{“ \% energy lost estimated ”}$$

$$Q_{\text{S}_{\text{air}}} = 1,1 \cdot V_{\text{air}} \cdot \Delta T$$

$$Q_{\text{L}_{\text{air}}} = 0,68 \cdot V_{\text{air}} \cdot \Delta w$$

$$Q_{\text{total}} = \sum Q_i$$

where,

$S_{\text{walls}}, S_{\text{windows}}$	are the walls and windows surface (m ²)
$U_{\text{walls}}, U_{\text{windows}}$	are the walls and windows thermal conductivity (W/m ² ·K)
ΔT	is the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures
N_{people}	is the number of people living in the dwelling (4)
F_{people}	is a factor describing the heat produced constantly by a human being
V_{air}	is the flow of air infiltrations (m ³ /h)
Δw	is the difference between the indoor and outdoor humidity

	Summer (W)	Winter (W)
Q_{windows}	367,91	-1193,22
Q_{walls}	3773,89	-12239,64
Q_{people}	674,22	674,22
Q_{Sair}	253,67	-822,74
Q_{Lair}	-1,93	6,05
Q_{devices}	400	400

Table 4.2. Heat balance

	Summer (kW)	Winter (kW)
Q_{total}	5,438	13,204
$Q_{\text{total corrected}}$	5,166	12,544
$Q_{\text{design Heat Pump}}$	5	12

Table 4.3. Power of the Heat Pump, results.

Table 4.2. shows the heat results obtained by the different heat sources. Finally, a correction factor (95%) has been applied in order to not oversize the heat pump installation, as it would increase the cost of the installation unnecessary, as the peak power is just needed for a few hours of the year.

The power results obtained to select the Heat Pump are on Table 4.3. As it can be seen on the last table, the energy demand, as predicted, is significantly larger for heating in winter than for cooling in summer.

The Heat Pump, using inverter technology, will be able to deliver both heat to the house, or inject it to the ground (cooling mode). As it will be connected with the geothermal system, the fluid exchanges heat with the ground, not with the outside air, as usual, increasing the performance of the heat pump (COP) making it more efficient, by also reducing the operational costs. This is due to the fact that the ground is usually cooler than the air in summer, and the other way around in winter, being the ground hotter than the air.

Figure 4.1. Heat Pump operation scheme. Source: [26]

5. Solar Thermal system

5.1. Introduction

Solar energy is a renewable energy source which can be converted into useful thermal energy by a Solar Thermal (ST) system. This thermal energy may be used directly or be converted to other kinds of energy, such as mechanical, electrical or chemical, in other cases. ST systems include equipment and devices, using fluid at low ($T < 100\text{ °C}$), medium ($100\text{ °C} < T < 400\text{ °C}$) or high ($T > 400\text{ °C}$) temperatures, depending on the system application. The most common ST application is the production of Domestic Hot Water (DHW).

For medium and high temperature applications, solar collectors utilize concentrating technology. Concentrating solar thermal (CST) systems use mirrors or lenses with tracking systems to focus a large area of sunlight onto a smaller area.

The available collector technologies

(Image 5.1.1.)

- » Collector without transparent cover (mainly used for swimming pools heating)
- » Flat plate collectors
- » Vacuum tube collectors
- » Compound parabolic concentrator collectors

Image 5.1.1. Low temperature Solar Thermal technologies

Commercial types of CST technologies

(Image 5.1.2.)

- » Parabolic through
- » Linear Fresnel
- » Central receiver, also called Solar Tower
- » Parabolic dish

Images 5.1.2. Medium & high temp. Solar Thermal technologies

TESSE²B project only uses solar thermal energy for low temperature applications, so the other technologies will no longer be discussed in this report.

ST systems which, besides DHW production, contribute to the space heating are called Solar Combi systems. Solar Combi systems are more commonly installed in Central and Northern Europe, where there is a long heating period. Of all the heating systems using solar energy, heated floors are the most accessible and offer the greatest advantages, mainly because they work at low temperatures and as a result, the overall efficiency is considerable.

The addition of thermal chiller in a Solar Combi system enables the system to address all building's thermal and cooling demands. These systems exploit the solar energy the whole year, by space heating in winter, solar cooling in summer and DHW throughout the year. Moreover, space cooling loads coincide with the high solar radiation and since the solar cooling system is heat driven, the building's electrical loads are reduced, as well as the problems associated with peak power demand during summer.

The main feature of a solar cooling system, besides the solar collector field, is the thermal chiller. On the thermal supply side, the ST system is rather conventional, consisting of high quality solar collectors, a storage circulation-hydraulic, control and back-up systems.

Two main solar cooling processes

- » Closed cycles, where absorption chillers produce chilled water for use in space conditioning equipment.
- » Open cycles, where desiccant evaporative cooling systems (DEC) produce chilled air for use in air conditioning equipment.

Figure 5.1.1. Solar Combi operation scheme. Source: [26]

Figure 5.1.2. Solar thermal application for heating and cooling. Source: [26]

5. Solar Thermal system

5.2. Solar Thermal in TESSE2B

The objective of TESSE2B project is to examine and optimize the ST and Geothermal systems by using PCM products in the thermal storage systems. The solar collectors will be able to both deliver the energy directly to the house appliances, or store it in the tanks when there is no demand, or the production exceeds the demand. In case the tank is already full, or the power to be stored is larger than the heating load capacity of the tank, part of the energy will have to be dissipated. For those cases, a heat dissipator is also installed, as it can be seen on *Figure 5.2.1*.

In the following figure the STS with PCM in the storage tanks for heating and cooling is presented. The heat pump could optionally be a Ground Source Heat Pump (GSHP).

As shown on the figure, the hydraulic system scheme offers many possibilities. Regarding the ST system on the left side, it can be seen that the pipes connect the solar collectors with both heat tank and DHW tank, both including PCM. A digital triode valve connected to the control system will be in charge to determine where the heat has to be delivered at all times.

Spain hydraulic scheme v7

Figure 5.2.1. TESSe2B hydraulic scheme

5. Solar Thermal system

5.2. Sizing and Calculations

Firstly, hourly values for a whole year from the solar radiation (direct and diffuse) were obtained using the meteorological station placed on the demosite. Also, the solar angle and azimuth had been taken into account. This values have been used as the initial data to make the sizing of the ST installation.

The collectors have been decided to be put south oriented and 52° degrees from the horizontal, which is found to be the optimal position to gather as much energy as possible. Therefore, the angle between the solar radiation and the solar collectors can be found through the following equation:

$$R_{direct} [W/m^2] = R_{solar} \cdot \cos(i) + [0,5 \cdot (1 + \cos(52)) \cdot R_{solar\ diffuse}] \cdot 1000$$

where,

R_{solar}	is the direct solar radiation from the sun to the ground.
$\cos(i)$	is the cosine of the angle between the sun rays and the panel surface. It varies throughout the day, as it depends on the solar altitude and azimuth.
$R_{solar\ diffuse}$	is the diffuse solar radiation from the sun.

By finally applying a performance factor, the radiation (W/m2) for every hour of the year, to be absorbed directly for th panels, has been found, which then can be multiplied by the total surface of the panels:

$$Solar\ Thermal\ Energy\ [W] = R_{direct} \cdot \eta \cdot S$$

Using these values, it is possible to determine the energy available depending on the solar collector's surface. Some tests were made to determine certain results of interest: "Código Técnico" [3] determines several parameters that have to be accomplished so a solar thermal installation is sized properly. When a ST system is used to cover just DHW needs...

- » It can't provide more than 110% of the energy demand at any month, or provide more than 100% for more than 3 months.
- » For the demosite's climatic characteristics, it has to deliver at least 50% of the energy related to DHW for the whole year.

Both values for the restrictions have been found, which are explained in the following tables:

Case 1: do not exceed 110% of the DHW demand
ST surface area: 2,2 m²

	DHW demand (kWh)	Energy covered by ST (kWh)	%
January	212,71	62,650	29,45
February	203,83	81,615	40,04
March	229,67	98,938	43,08
April	215,46	114,556	53,17
May	210,83	131,972	62,59
June	183,13	120,835	65,98
July	170,44	174,081	102,13
August	156,80	170,304	108,61
September	147,69	109,310	74,01
October	159,32	90,413	56,75
November	168,36	54,431	32,33
December	192,86	59,330	30,76
TOTAL	2251,16	1268,44	56,35

Case 2: cover at least 50% of the total DHW demand
ST surface area: 2 m²

	DHW demand (kWh)	Energy covered by ST (kWh)	%
January	212,71	62,650	29,45
February	203,83	81,615	40,04
March	229,67	98,938	43,08
April	215,46	114,556	53,17
May	210,83	131,972	62,59
June	183,13	120,835	65,98
July	170,44	174,081	102,13
August	156,80	170,304	108,61
September	147,69	109,310	74,01
October	159,32	90,413	56,75
November	168,36	54,431	32,33
December	192,86	59,330	30,76
TOTAL	2251,16	1268,44	56,35

Tables 5.3.1 and 5.3.2. Solar Thermal sizing results for Domestic Hot Water application

5. Solar Thermal system

5.2. Sizing and Calculations

By seeing the results, it is clear that if the purpose of use the ST system was just to cover the energy needs for DHW, the possibilities of installing the collectors are reduced to an area between 2 and 2,2 square meters.

However, in Tesse2B case, the purpose is to cover 30% of the total demand, which consists in DHW and also heating/cooling needs, so another simulation has been made comparing the heat production by the collectors with the total energy demand. “Código Técnico”[3] indicates that this is possible while it includes a heat dissipation device when there’s excess production periods, or another way to distribute the energy. Here are the results:

Case 3: cover 30% of the Total Yearly Demand

ST surface area: 5 m²

	Total demand (kWh)	Energy covered by ST (kWh)	%
January	1742,71	142,387	8,17
February	1359,22	185,488	13,65
March	1109,95	224,859	20,26
April	788,54	260,354	33,02
May	320,34	299,937	93,63
June	183,16	274,625	149,93
July	170,44	395,638	232,12
August	156,80	387,055	246,83
September	147,69	248,432	168,21
October	253,46	205,485	81,07
November	924,56	123,708	13,38
December	1487,60	134,841	9,06
TOTAL	8644,52	2882,81	33,35

Table 5.3.3. Solar Thermal sizing results for DHW and heating

At first glance, it is noticeable that the ST system profile behaves as opposed to how the heating demand does it, as the collectors are able to produce more energy in summer, when the demand is lower, and are not capable to produce much energy in winter, when the demand is higher but, on the contrary, there are less sunny hours. This creates a contrasting situation. When looking at the right column, it can be seen that in summer, the ST production exceeds the demand, producing more than twice the demand (more than 200%), whereas in winter, specifically in December and January, it doesn't even reach 10% of the demand.

This makes obvious the need of an energy storage system, so not only can store energy during the day to use it at night, but also store some extra energy in summer to use it in winter (seasonal storage), when solar hours decrease significantly, and the collectors cannot collect much energy.

However, it is worth mentioning that these results come from an ideal case. In a real situation, as it will be discussed later on the report, there would be losses when storing the energy, and also in the tank. In addition, not all the energy will be used directly from the panels to the house appliances, as the demand profile might not match with the solar production profile.

The collectors model used for the project is about **2,3 m² for each panel**. When taking into account the losses, the sizing increases significantly. Also, it has been decided that two of the panels will be disconnected during summer, so less excess energy has to be dissipated, and more panels can be installed, seeking for a more balanced situation between the winter case and summer case (See final results on chapter 9).

6. Geothermal Borehole Heat Exchangers

6.1. Introduction

Geothermal energy consists in the heat exchange between the habitable parts of the house and the ground. The operation is similar to a regular heat pump, which generally exchanges heat with the ambient air. Geothermal systems take benefit of the fact that the ground is warmer than the air in winter, and cooler than the air in summer, increasing the performance of the heat pump. Generally, utilization is based on a geothermal doublet, where one well is used as producer and one as injector. Reinjection of the fluids after utilization is essential for preserving the natural pressure conditions in the aquifer. Geothermal projects without reinjection have seen tremendous pressure drawdown which can reduce the productivity of neighboring wells and can lead to subsidence in the meter range.

The geothermal fluid is pumped to the surface with the help of an electrical submersible pump (ESP). Lineshaft pumps which have their motor at surface are less common in Mid Europe. Temperatures higher than 120 °C are still an issue for the ESP's, causing long downtimes for repairs or replacing the device. Precipitation of carbonate and sulphide minerals has turned out to put threat to projects in the temperature range over 100 °C. To prevent degassing and change in the partial pressure of carbon dioxide which can lead to heavy carbonate precipitation, well head pressures in the order of >15 bar are recommended. These pressures have to be generated by the pump; therefore, the pump design is a critical path in geothermal installation.

For the heat transfer at the surface heat exchangers are used. In the heat exchanger the geothermal fluid and the working fluid of the grid are separated in order to prevent mixing of the fluids. In district heating systems the working fluid is circulated in the geothermal grid by transmission pumps. The biggest advantage of geothermal energy lies in their basic load capacity. This results in a large number of annual full load hours.

Borehole heat exchangers (BHEs) are an effective way of utilizing shallow geothermal energy. The critical path in the completion of a borehole heat exchanger is the installation of the pipes and the grouting. The grouting has to ensure the heat transfer to the circulating fluid and has to seal the annulus thus preventing uncontrolled flow of fluids or gases. Ascending or descending fluids can be an issue in sedimentary sequences with successions of permeable and less permeable strata of different pressure regimes. In areas where drinking water supply relies on ground water from deeper confined strata, a concentration of BHEs with defective annulus sealings can lead to a significant pressure drop in the deep systems when groundwater can ascend to unconfined aquifers at or near the surface. This issue effected the prohibition of BHEs or depth restriction in some sensitive areas in Austria.

Images 6.1.1 (previous page) and 6.1.2. Drilling machine. Source: [26]

Both images above show the machines used to drill the ground. The pipes where the fluid will circulate will be installed in the inside of those holes. These pipes make an “U” shape, so the cold fluid goes down and returns, gathering heat from the ground, or viceversa, injecting the heat to the ground, depending if the system is being used for heating or cooling the dwelling. In other words, these systems work like a reversible refrigerator by removing heat from the underground and rejecting it into the building in the heating mode and vice versa in the cooling mode.

Since GCHP systems are high efficiency systems that are installed in low-energy consumption buildings, the target is always optimising system parameters as well as the overall system design and operation in order to maximize COP (Coefficient of Performance) and SPF (Seasonal Performance Factor). The main parameter in order to get the optimum system operation is the heat pump which is the core of the system. This can be achieved by the use of a heat pump either with an inverter in compressor or with compressors in series (large systems with capacities higher than 60 kWth) in order to adjust the heat pump (compressor) operation according to the user’s energy profile. On the other hand, the overall system operation can be adjusted by the use of inverter circulators in order to minimize the electricity consumption.

The overall energy consumption can be minimized as in all heating/cooling systems by the use of a compensation system.

6. Geothermal Borehole Heat Exchangers

6.1. Introduction

Ground Coupled Heat Pumps for heating, cooling and domestic hot water production are used in moderate climates, especially in Mediterranean countries, where heating is necessary during the winter but also cooling during the summer due to quite high temperatures. In these cases, the refrigeration cycle must be reversible from the heating to cooling mode and vice versa so a 4-way valve is necessary.

This valve can be added externally to the refrigeration cycle when the heat pump is designed only for heating.

Image 6.1.3. Borehole Heat Exchangers scheme

Figure 6.1.1. 4-way valve operation

Moreover, in order to produce cooling and DHW simultaneously there are three alternatives:

- » Reverse instantaneously from cooling to heating mode for DHW production. In case of significant DHW needs a separate heat pump for DHW is used.
- » Heat pump with desuperheater in the refrigeration cycle with relatively reduced heat pump efficiency.
- » Rejection heat of the condenser to the DHW tank using a heating element to increase temperature since the outlet condensing temperature is about 30°C.

6.2. Sizing the pipe's depth

The most crucial point in planning a GSHP-System is to determine the length and the configuration of the BHEs. A balance between the requirements of the heating system and economic considerations has to be found: too short BHEs will cause severe restrictions in the performance of the heat pump, as it will be forced to work at lower outflow temperatures of the BHEs thus decreasing the **COP**. On the other side, the construction of the BHEs is one of the most cost-intensive parts of the system, so a larger number of BHE-meters can make the whole project uneconomic.

The basic parameters for the final layout of a BHE-system are:

- » The requirements of the building, such as heating and/or cooling power, the annual energy used for heating/cooling (and the distribution during the year), domestic hot water, etc. Note that this energy demand is estimated to be 70% of the total demand, as 30% should be covered by the Solar Thermal system.
- » The geological setting of the site (see chapter 2.2 and 3.1), defining the underground temperature and the specific heat extraction.
- » Available space.

Taking into account all these data, the reference heat pump used to calculate the length of the pipes is the one found before (see chapter 4), having 12 kW for heating and 5 kW for cooling. The water temperatures at the beginning and end of the pipes, and at the entrance and exit of the condenser and evaporator, are the generally estimated for this kind of study:

Water	Inlet T (pipes)	Outlet T (pipes)	Water	Inlet T (circuit)	Outlet T (circuit)
Summer (°C)	35	30	Condenser	7	12
Winter (°C)	5	15	Evaporator	45	40

Tables 6.2.1 and 6.2.2. Heat Pump data

6. Geothermal Borehole Heat Exchangers

6.2. Sizing the pipe's depth

Then, using the demand profile and the temperature profile, it has been able to determine the building load, which points out the power the heat pump has to deliver depending on the outlet temperature, to be able to reach comfort temperatures both in winter and summer. This values, divided by the total power of the heat pump, give us the so called Load Factor. This factor gives an idea on how hard the heat pump will have to be working depending on the ambient temperature, to properly heat the house. The results obtained are represented on the next graph:

Figure 6.2.3. Heat Pump's Load Factor

Figure 6.2.3 allows us to see that the heat pump is well sized, as it won't be able to supply all needed heat but only if temperatures happen to be lower than -2 °C, approximately, which apparently is out of the temperature range of the demosite. Nevertheless, if this occurred, it is better to not be able to cover the demand for just a few hours every year than installing a more powerful heat pump, which increases the cost of the whole installation, and does not compensate with the increase in energy supply capacity.

Another interesting fact is that it can be seen the outside temperature range in which the heat pump does not need to work, assuming that the temperature indise the house is already at comfort levels, and therefore, confort levels will be maintained naturally thanks to the walls isolation.

The borehole depth has been determined after fixing some design parameters. The pipe diameter is going to be about 40 mm, having a thickness of 3,7 mm. The borehole diameter is going to be 132 mm.

Then, there are two ways in which the BHEs can be sized. One option is to take into account the heating demand to calculate the depth of the borehole, and the other way is to calculate it using the cooling demand as reference. Both options have been estimated. However, as it can be seen on table 6.2.1, the sizing from cooling is very much smaller than the heating ones, and this is because the demand is basically focused on heating.

This means that if the BHEs can supply the heating demand, they will be able to also work properly for cooling, as it requires less power, as seen before on the report. *Table 6.2.1* shows the results (the first two lines for heating, and the last one for cooling), which indicate the total tube length required to exchange enough heat with the ground, and possible number of tubes to achieve this heat exchange.

Length of the tubes (Heating / Cooling)	W/m of tube	Depth for one single tube "U"	Chosen number of tubes	Real depth
385,3 m	31,15	192,63	2	96,31 m
385,3 m	31,15	192,63	4	48,16 m
39,7 m	125,86	19,86	1	19,86 m

Table 6.2.1. BHE sizing results

Two options are feasible for the project. The first might be installing **two pipes of 96,31 m** depth, and the other to use **4 pipes** but just **48,16 m** depth each. Both options sized for heating, as explained before. As the objectives of the project are not only to develop a working installation, but also to search and test innovative solutions, the project partners agreed to use 4 pipes, so two of them will have PCM inside the boreholes, and the others not, to be able to compare to what extent they affect on the heat pump performance, despite probably being a slightly more expensive solution. In a normal case, probably the optimal solution would be to use just two pipes, as the required depth is still relatively low, for a geothermal installation.

7. PCM integration into BHE and Storage Tanks

7.1. Introduction to Thermal Energy Storage (TES)

Thermal energy storage (TES) refers to the technology that allows the transfer and storage of heat energy or, alternatively, energy from ice or cold air or water. This method is built into new technologies that complement energy solutions such as solar and hydro. The aim is to bridge the time gap between energy requirement and energy use.

Depending on the specific technology, it allows excess thermal energy to be stored and used hours, days, or months later, at scales ranging from individual process, building, multiuser-building, district, town, or region. Usage examples are the balancing of energy demand between daytime and nighttime, storing summer heat for winter heating, or winter cold for summer air conditioning (Seasonal Thermal Energy Storage). Storage media include water or ice-slush tanks in most cases, masses of native earth or bedrock accessed with heat exchangers by means of boreholes, deep aquifers contained between impermeable strata; shallow, lined pits filled with gravel and water and insulated at the top, as well as eutectic solutions and, in some recent cases, phase change materials.

The idea behind TES is changing the way users generate the vast amount of heating and cooling capacity that eats up so much conventional energy from the grid. The problem is that much of the grid power used for heating and cooling buildings is generated by energy from fossil fuels such as coal, oil and natural gas. This can be addressed using TES, which can provide heating and cooling solutions simply by evening out the distributed heat in a natural landscape or cycle, for example, by applying heat stored in solar collectors or by distributing cold water or air from underground to cool a building space. Scientists and engineers are hard at work on new thermal energy storage solutions to replace fossil fuel-driven HVAC systems.

7.2 What is a PCM? Pros and cons against water

Traditionally, thermal energy has been stored as sensible heat, such as in a conventional domestic hot water tank. Recently, there has been a movement towards storing this heat as latent heat instead.

Figure 7.2.1. Sensible and Latent heat

As it can be seen on the graph above, sensible heat storage occurs when increasing the temperature of a certain fluid or material, whereas latent heat is given when there's a phase change in a certain fluid or material, which is a process that does not increase the temperature of the given material.

Phase change materials, commonly referred to as PCMs, are products that store and release thermal energy during the processes of melting and freezing. This cycle of melting and freezing can occur countless times without degradation. This is because there is no chemical reaction involved, only physical processes.

Despite water can act as a PCM in some cases, it has been widely used in its sensible region, heating up large amounts of water up to temperatures from 60 to 80°C, depending on the case (always below its evaporation).

However, in the recent years, it has been discovered that latent heat storage offers a lot of benefits when comparing it to **traditional methods**:

» The heat losses to the surroundings are lower, as the material does not change its temperature during the process. Many studies have demonstrated that the wider is the difference between the ambient temperature and the temperature inside the storage tank, the greater the losses will be (see reference [9]). Keeping the storage tank at a temperature closer to the outside air makes the storage system more efficient.

» It makes the control system more natural and simple, as stores and releases the heat always at the same temperature, which can also be selected depending on the chosen PCM, and can also be closer to the temperature at which the DHW is demanded.

» It has a higher energy density. This means that less volume is required to store the same energy, when using a PCM instead of a traditional sensible heat storage system. This is a very important aspect, as the main problem with hot water tanks has always been its size, which also adds to the building costs. Having a smaller tank makes a PCM solution much more easy to integrate into a residential heating storage system.

7. PCM integration into BHE and Storage Tanks

7.3. Integrating PCMs as a solution for Thermal Storage

There are many materials known and available to use, and each of them has its own melting/freezing point. That is the key parameter to take into account, and determines which materials are feasible for the project. The materials which have been more popular in recent years are listed below:

» **Salt Hydrates** are compounds of salt and water and have the advantage of high latent heat of fusion due to their high water content. The introduction of salts into the water can both raise and lower the freezing point of the water. This allows a range of PCMs to be created that all have different applications. A disadvantage of using these salts is the potential for phase segregation during the charging and discharging of the PCM. This is where heavier salt settles at the bottom of the solution and consequently, the TES capacity of the solution changes. This can have major impacts on the lifetime of the PCM storage.

» **Eutectics** are mixtures of two or more substances mixed in such a way as to provide the desired melting/freezing point. The mixture melts completely at the design temperature and has the overall composition in both liquid and solid phases which has the main criteria of a PCM.

» **Organics** are materials which are blends of paraffins and fatty alcohols. These PCMs have the advantage of being very chemically stable, however due to their lower density they can store less heat in a given space than salt hydrate PCM. Additionally they have poor thermal conductivity and are relatively expensive.

» **Solid-Solid PCMs** that undergo a solid/solid phase transition with the associated absorption and release large amounts of heat are the latest addition to PCM range. These materials change their crystalline structure from one lattice configuration to another at a fixed and well-defined temperature, and the transformation can involve latent heats comparable to the most effective solid/liquid PCMs. Such materials are useful because, unlike solid/liquid PCMs, they do not require nucleation to prevent supercooling. Additionally, because it is a solid/solid phase change, there is no visible change in the appearance of the PCM (other than a slight expansion/contraction), and there are no problems associated with handling liquids, i.e. containment, potential leakage, etc. There is a range of different PCMs available and so they must be carefully considered for any given application.

	Advantages	Disadvantages
Organic	Simple to use Non-corrosive No Supercooling No nucleating agents	Generally more expensive Low latent heat/density Often have a broader melting range Can be combustible
Salt-based	Generally cheaper High latent heat/density Well defined phase change temperatures Non flammable	Needs careful preparation Needs additives to stabilize for long term use Prone to supercooling Can be corrosive to some metals

Table 7.3.1. Characteristics of PCMs. Source: PCM products sales documents

Since the actual system is working with domestic hot water, which is demanded approximately at 45°C, it has been needed to identify which materials melt/freeze at that approximate temperature, to be used as the hot tank solution.

Figure 7.3.2. Melting temperatures and enthalpy of different PCMs. Source: IEA ECES Final Report

As it can be seen on the graph, there are various options which could be used for TESS^e2B solution, such as paraffines, clathrates, fatty acids, polyethylene or glycols, when looking at the desired temperature range. However, not all materials perform equally when being used to store heat, so it is needed to search for the optimum material in terms of cost, conductivity, heat transfer rate, encapsulation, etc.

7. PCM integration into BHE and Storage Tanks

7.3. Integrating PCMs as a solution for Thermal Storage

Paraffin wax in particular has attracted attention because of its low cost, stability and chemical inertness. However, paraffin wax, in common with many phase change materials, has low thermal conductivity, which inhibits quick heat transfer and thus limits its use as an energy storage material.

In order to overcome the thermal conductivity problem, common in many phase change materials, a number of different nanoparticle suspensions have been explored to enhance the performance of the material, such as carbon-based nanostructures (nanofibers, nanoplatelets, graphite nanoparticles, graphene flakes and carbon nanotubes), metallic (Ag, Al, Cu, Fe) and metal oxides (Al₂O₃, CuO, Fe₃O₄, TiO₂) nanoparticles. It was found that in general, carbon based nanostructures and carbon nanotubes exhibit by far greater enhancement of thermal conductivity in comparison to metallic/metal oxide nanoparticles.

The so called nanofluids are defined as fluids with nanoparticle suspensions. Adding nanoparticles ranging from 1 to 100 nm can have a large effect on the thermal conductivity of the overall material, making nanofluids attractive from a cost effect point of view as well. In addition, particles such as nanofibers, carbon nanotubes, or nanowires were found to be the best to enhance thermal conductivity.

In Tesse2b, it has been chosen to work with exfoliated expanded graphite nanoplatelets of differing sizes, aspect ratios and surface area. The nanoplatelets have an in-plane and out-of-plane thermal conductivity of 3000 and 6 W/mK respectively. They were chosen because of their superior thermal conductivity, comparable to that of carbon nanotubes, at a much less cost and thus feasible for applications. They also come with high dimensional aspect ratios and can be tailored to different sizes.

After trying different aspect ratios and particle sizes, the results to enhance the material properties are presented on the following figures:

Figure 7.3.3 and 7.3.4. Measured thermal conductivity and heat fusion of paraffin wax with graphite nanoplatelets

The largest increase can be seen to occur for the M15 sample in the low weight fraction regime up to 1% and at 6% weight fraction. The thermal conductivity is increased 100% to the value of 0.44W/mK from the 0.22W/mK for pure paraffin for 1% weight fraction (~0.4% volume fraction) and almost 250% at 6% weight fraction (~2.6% volume fraction).

The heat of fusion is gradually reduced with the increase of weight fraction to about 10% for a 6% weight fraction, in sample M15, which again its performing best. Similar trend is seen for the samples with C750 nanoplatelets. Interestingly, the M5 nanoplatelets seem to leave the heat of fusion largely unaffected up to 6% weight fraction.

In conclusion, sample M15, which consisted in paraffin wax with cylinder graphite nanoplatelets with

Diameter = 15 nm

Depth = 6-8 nm

Surface Area = 120-150 m²/g

Is the material which improves the thermal properties the most.

8. Whole system integration and performance

After sizing the elements, its time to integrate the different parts as a whole. To find the optimum values, and also determine the energy savings in terms of consumption provided by the use of PCM, two different scenarios are presented: the first one, using solar thermal, borehole heat exchangers, and a hot water tank as the storage system; the second one, using also solar thermal and borehole heat exchangers, but using PCM tanks as the storage system.

Calculations for both cases allow tracking the energy supply and demand for every hour, during a whole year. It has been assumed that all the demand is always covered regarding the heating, cooling, and domestic hot water needs. The main variables to be modified in order to determine the final solution are:

- » Solar panels surface area (m^2)
- » Maximum energy storage capacity (kWh) of the tanks, which is directly related to the total tank volume (m^3)
- » Maximum heat charge or discharge power of the tanks (kW)
- » Energy losses in the tank per hour (kWh)

8.1 Operation

The system has many possibilities to operate in order to satisfy the energy demand. In this section, the different operation modes are explained into more detail:

First, it is supposed that the heating, cooling, and DHW demand is known for every hour of the year, when making the simulations.

Then, as the hourly solar radiation (kW/m^2) is also known, by modifying the collectors surface, the available heat from solar thermal technology is found. This energy can be directly used when there is demand at the same time it is produced, or stored in the tanks when there is no demand, or the production exceeds the demand.

The energy coming from solar thermal collectors can be stored in the tanks except in two occasions. When the tank is already full, the excess heat is dissipated through the heat dissipator. Also, if the power load exceeds the load capacity of the tank,

then the tank fills up at maximum power, and the excess energy is also dissipated. When the tank is partially or full load, energy losses are taken into account to happen continuously. It is worth saying that the stratification and wall losses in the tank have been found to be much more lower in the PCM solution than in a conventional hot water tank.

If the energy demand cannot be covered by the solar thermal technology nor the storage system, it is supplied by the heat pump, circulating the fluid through the borehole heat exchangers, and using electricity from the grid to run the engines.

The final algorithm will be able to store energy coming from the heat pump as well. This operation mode is interesting when the price of electricity drops, or in case the weather predictions indicate that the solar radiation will be significantly reduced in the following days. However, these facts have not been considered when making the simulations, due to the unpredictability of this data.

8.2. Results

Simulations using different values for the number of solar panels have been made, and also varying the tank capacity, for both storage technologies: using a conventional hot water tank and using a PCM tank. As one solar panel has 2,3 square meter surface, the simulations vary from a range between 2 and 9 panels (4,6 and 20,7 m²). The tank storage capacity has been tested between three different options: 48, 64 or 80 kWh storage capacity for both (storage method) cases. The maximum charge and discharge power of the tank is 5,6 kW for both cases as well. The following tables present a possible solution, which is a good example to compare the performance of both energy storage systems under the same conditions. All the other results appear on the report's Annex, page 18.

WATER TANK DATA

Maximum storage	64 kWh
Charge/discharge Power	5,6 kW
Volume	0,765 m ³
Losses per hour	0,650 kWh

PCM TANK DATA

Maximum storage	64 kWh
Charge/discharge Power	5,6 kW
Volume	0,306 m ³
Losses per hour	0,294 kWh

6 Solar Thermal Panels; 13,8 m²

WATER TANK	Energy (kWh)	%
Total demand	8644,529	100%
Total energy from solar	2582,910	29,87
Covered directly	741,786	8,51
Storage System	1841,12	21,29
Energy covered by Heat Pump	6061,618	70,12
Electricity used by Heat Pump	1347,026	15,58
Total Energy dissipated	833,999	9,64
Total renewable energy	7297,50	84,41

6 Solar Thermal Panels; 13,8 m²

PCM TANK	Energy (kWh)	%
Total demand	8644,529	100%
Total energy from solar	3162,482	36,58
Covered directly	741,786	8,51
Storage System	2420,695	28,00
Energy covered by Heat Pump	5482,04	63,41
Electricity used by Heat Pump	1218,232	14,09
Total Energy dissipated	2185,499	32,56
Total renewable energy	7426,296	85,90

Tables 8.2.1. Simulation results example. Comparison between two Thermal Energy Storage systems

8. Whole system integration and performance

8.2. Results

The simulations contemplate the use of PCM as the hot storage system. Unfortunately, it has not been possible to integrate the use of PCMs in the boreholes, which would made the calculations become significantly more complex. Nonetheless, it is still in experimental phase, and its effect it is yet under study. However, its operation is explained in the next paragraph:

The idea is to use a different PCM than in the hot tanks. In this time, the melting point is wanted to be lower but close to the ground's average temperature for the whole year (Figure 8.2.2, blue line). In winter, when BHEs extract heat from the ground, they lower the ground's temperature, and viceversa in summer. Having a PCM placed in the boreholes could prevent to have drastic temperature drops, as the material has the ability to freeze before cooling the ground (Figure 8.2.2, red line). Afterwards, when ground temperature becomes stable again, PCMs would melt to return to the initial state, making them able to act again as a barrier against temperature drops when necessary. This enhances the heat pump's performance, as it increases the gap between the temperature of the fluid and the ground.

The next Figure represents this functionality:

Figure 8.2.2. Representation of the effect of PCMs into boreholes heat exchangers

As it can be seen, whenever the ground temperature passes through the melting/freezing point of the PCM, this one changes its phase, retaining the heat, and therefore avoiding the ground to reach very low temperatures (Figure 8.2.2, red line).

The weakest link in borehole HEs is the heat transfer in the ground that is mainly conductive and its thermal diffusivity is low. This leads to a much slower ground thermal response than the heat pump requirements, resulting in thermal waves being transmitted into the ground through the BHEs causing lower coefficient of performance (COP) of ground source heat pumps (GSHP). To improve the effectiveness of BHEs, mixing PCMs directly with backfill material for the grout is the innovative solution thought for this project. Employing PCMs is an effective way to store thermal energy in the BHEs and smooth the generated thermal wave. Among the available PCMs, the organic paraffin is the one to be selected and integrated to BHEs because it is environmental friendly. The PCM will be encapsulated and blend with soil/water to form the borehole grout. Inside the BHEs there will be two types of PCM in case there's need for seasonal charge/discharge cycles.

Back to the results, as it can be seen on the simulations, there are noticeable differences between the two cases. Firstly, it is important to note that for the same storage capacity, the PCM tank occupies less than half the volume of the water tank (see table 8.2.1), which makes it easy to integrate in a closet inside the house, instead of having a large tank outside the house, which would be more affected by the outside temperature.

As the temperature inside the hot PCM tank is much lower than in the water tank (45 °C vs 80°C), the heat losses are also lower, as its closer to the ambient temperature and, therefore, the gap between both temperatures is narrower.

This shows a clear improvement regarding the energy used through the storage system, which increases approximately by 7% when using PCM instead of a water tank (see Figure 8.2.3 below). As a consequence, the heat pump doesn't need to deliver as much energy, and the overall system uses more renewable energy and less electricity from the grid.

Figure 8.2.3. Simulation results. Yearly Stored Energy comparison

On the other hand, it can be seen that the PCM case has to dissipate more energy coming from the solar thermal collectors (see Figure 8.2.4). As said, the losses in the PCM tank are lower (less than half of those occurring on the water tank). This makes it easy for the tank to become full, and in that point is where most of the solar thermal energy has to be dissipated. This could be compensated having a larger tank, or less solar panels. Nonetheless, it is still a better solution than the hot water tank, even if some energy has to be dissipated, in terms of efficiency and general performance of the whole system. In fact, the periods in which the tank is at full storage have been identified, and are just happening a few days in summer, when the demand is very low, whereas the production can be very high, which is fairly reasonable to happen.

8. Whole system integration and performance

8.2. Results

Figure 8.2.4. Simulation results. Yearly Dissipated Energy comparison

Not that this dissipated energy is not related to the energy losses. It counts as the energy produced that the tank is not able to store. PCM tanks have to dissipate more energy because they are more efficient when storing it, and can stay for longer periods at full storage (less losses).

Overall, the number of solar panels is the parameter which affects the most the energy production and the whole renewable factor. The tank size affects the system in a less way. A larger tank reduces the energy dissipation and enhances the energy stored throughout the year, but this does not compensate with its increase in cost. This is due to the fact that the dissipation is basically happening during July in August, which is when the system is oversized, and easily exceeds the tank's capacity in all cases.

As the study is not focused in seasonal storage, having a huge storage tank does not adapt with the project's purpose, but could be an option to study in this particular case.

However, the difference between a water tank and a PCM tank stays clear comparing all simulations, being the PCM solution a much more efficient one.

Renewable Energy (% of Total Demand)

Figure 8.2.5. Simulation results. Yearly Dissipated Energy comparison

As commented before, the graphs show that the tank size is the less affecting variable. The key aspects to look at when making the installation are the number of solar panels, which are be sized according to the given house, as well as the borehole heat exchangers, and the most important, choose a TES_{Se2B} solution instead of a conventional hot water tank, as it is a more efficient solution and helps reducing even more the use of electricity from the grid, making more use of renewable energy (Figure 8.2.5). In the next part, the economical and environmental aspects of the project are discussed.

9. Economical and Environmental Analysis

9.1. Scope

Before digging into the economical aspects of the project, it is important to take a look at its market possibilities and point out which is the current scenario in terms of energy consumption for heating, cooling, and domestic hot water needs.

Heating and cooling accounted for 50% (1,102 Mtoe) of EU's final energy consumption in 2012, thus being its biggest energy sector. In addition, heating and cooling is projected to remain the largest energy sector by 2030 and 2050, either in a business-as-usual scenario, or in a decarbonisation scenario. Heating and cooling can be categorized into six different categories among all sectors: space heating, space cooling, water heating, process heating, process cooling and other uses (including cooking).

Figure 9.1.1. Final energy consumption for heating and cooling, 2012.
Source: European Commission

The household sector accounted for almost 25% of the final energy consumption of EU-28 in 2014; therefore, it was the 3rd largest consumer of energy, after the transport (33.2%) and industry (25.9%) sectors (Figure 25). Figure 26 shows the share of the different energy products covering the final energy consumption of households. The largest part of energy consumed by households is covered by natural gas (35.6%) and electricity (25.0%). Renewable energy sources account just for 15.7%, petroleum products for 12.7% and derived heat for 7.8%; the smallest share belongs to solid fuels, which cover 3.3%.

As it can be seen, there's still a huge dependance on non renewable energy sources to cover heating and cooling needs, so this means there's a lot of possibilities for a renewable system to be competitive in the market nowadays.

Figure 9.1.2. Final energy consumption, EU-28, 2014. Source: Eurostat

Figure 9.1.3. Final energy consumption of households by product in the EU, 2015. Source: Eurostat

Heat and cool cannot be transported on a long distance, thus being produced and consumed locally. This leads to fragmented and local heating and cooling markets, comprising of many different technologies and stakeholders (installers, engineers, energy advisors, energy service/utility companies). Heating and cooling is directly connected with other energy markets, namely fuel (oil, natural gas, etc.) and electricity, as well as with other markets such as real estate and technology.

On the contrary, the global market for Advanced Phase Change Materials (PCM) is estimated to reach 1.5\$ billion by 2020. Energy conservation and more strict regulations for greenhouse gas emissions are among the main factors assisting the development of the industry. On the contrary, main barriers of the industry's deployment are high cost and lack of consumer awareness. Europe represents the largest PCM market worldwide. Heating, ventilation, air-conditioning and refrigeration, as well as the building and construction industry represent the largest end-use markets for advanced PCM. Bio-based advanced PCM is the fastest growing market section, while paraffin-based PCM is the largest segment, representing approximately 50% of the global 2015 market.

9. Economical and Environmental Analysis

9.2. Market survey

An online questionnaire survey was conducted between June 2016 and February 2017. The questionnaire was prepared by partner IPS, with the collaboration of partners CRES, TEISTE, ECOSERVEIS and GEOTEAM and included four sections of questions: a) personal interests about environmental and energy issues, b) TESSE2B solution: intention to use, c) housing/household characterization and d) sociodemographic information; additionally, the questionnaire also included a short description of the TESSE2B solution. Aim of the survey was to examine the acceptance of TESSE2B solution through self-reported behavioural intention, which is based on the socio-cognitive theory.

The survey, which aimed at the general public without any demographic restrictions, was conducted in five different countries by the corresponding partners: Austria (GEOTEAM), Germany (RUB), Greece (CRES and TEISTE), Portugal (IPS) and Spain (ECOSERVEIS).

The full results of the survey can be found and download on TESSe2B's official website (Deliverable section). Nonetheless, the most interesting and important information extracted from the questionnaires is listed below:

- » More than 70% of the participants showed interest in energy efficiency and reducing the green house gas emissions in Spain (more than in the other countries).
- » In southern countries (Spain, Portugal and Greece) more people have invested in thermal energy systems in the last 5 years.
- » In Spain, approximately half of those have invested in a renewable energy system, and only 14% have acquired a thermal storage system.
- » In south, there's more people who believe that TESSe2B can improve their quality life, as well as reducing its energy expenses and, therefore, save some money. Northern countries may be more familiar with renewable technologies, and maybe it is somehow more present than in southern countries, which would mean that in some dwellings, integrating the TESSe2B solution may not imply significant changes, if nowadays they already own a energy storage system.
- » On the other hand, northern countries are willing to pay more money than the rest. Whereas in Germany or Austria, participants would pay around 6000 €, in Spain, Portugal and Greece, people are willing to pay around 3000 € for the TESSe2B solution.
- » Regarding the payback period, the trend is more or less the same. In the north it is expected between 5 and 8 years, but in south is expected to be between 3 and 5 years. Note that the perception of the financial aspects is usually related with the monthly income.
- » Given the information provided by the users, it can be assumed that TESSe2B solution will have more impact on single dwelling houses, and therefore is the principal market to focus on.

9.3. Economical analysis

To evaluate the feasibility of the project, it is necessary to estimate its payback period, among other things. Although the renewable technologies are necessary to implement the TESSe2B solution, the economic analysis focuses mainly on the thermal storage system, as it is the product to be sold to potential clients, which could already have solar and/or geothermal system installed in their house, and that's why the installation costs for other renewable technologies have not been taken into account. In addition, every case is different, as the energy demand varies according to multiple factors, and it is thought to have more sense to focus just on the storage system. If not, the initial costs would have an enormous variability.

The following table (9.3.1) gives an overview of the energy stored yearly and the payback period for clients that acquire the PCM TESSe2B solution as the first source of storage system. In this example, for a tank about 48 kWh of storage capacity. The next one (Table 9.3.2) represents the payback period when acquiring a water tank (same storage capacity) as the source of storage system, so both options can be compared from an economical point of view, for different scenarios depending on the number of solar thermal panels. The savings represent the money earned as a result of having the PCM tank or water tank instead of not having any storage system.

PCM tank, 48 kWh capacity

n° of Solar Collectors	Net Energy Stored (kWh)	Electricity Price (€/kWh)	Savings per year (€)	Price of the Tank (€)	Payback Period (years)
2	508,671	0,15	76,300	3000	39,318
3	1107,083	0,15	166,062	3000	18,065
4	1680,096	0,15	252,014	3000	11,904
5	2086,537	0,15	312,980	3000	9,585
6	2392,121	0,15	358,818	3000	8,360
7	2618,148	0,15	392,722	3000	7,638
8	2789,722	0,15	418,458	3000	7,169
9	2917,724	0,15	437,658	3000	6,854

Table 9.3.1. Economic Analysis of the PCM solution for energy storage

Water tank, 48 kWh capacity (aprox 570 liters)

n° of Solar Collectors	Net Energy Stored (kWh)	Electricity Price (€/kWh)	Savings per year (€)	Price of the Tank (€)	Payback Period (years)
2	207,676	0,15	31,151	3133	100,573
3	515,380	0,15	77,307	3133	40,526
4	1009,518	0,15	151,427	3133	20,689
5	1484,391	0,15	222,658	3133	14,070
6	1817,922	0,15	272,688	3133	11,489
7	2028,796	0,15	304,319	3133	10,295
8	2195,192	0,15	329,278	3133	9,514
9	2307,726	0,15	346,158	3133	9,050

Table 9.3.2. Economic Analysis of a conventional hot water tank for energy storage

9. Economical and Environmental Analysis

9.3. Economical analysis

As it can be seen, the PCM tanks are a more profitable option than the water tank, in several aspects. The price for the water tank has been estimated based on the research of existing tanks available in the market and their respective prices (see references [17], [20] and [28]). The PCM tank price is estimated through data provided by the project managers, but the price is still under optimization.

As more solar collectors take part in the system, the payback period of PCM and the one of a water solution become closer. This is due to the fact that the energy losses, which are the main difference when comparing the two types of storage, become less significant as more solar panels are installed in the house. So, for usual systems with for example 4 solar panels, the differences can be quite high, as it can be seen on the tables 9.3.1. and 9.3.2. Results comparing tanks with a storage capacity of 64 kWh and 80 kWh can be found in the Annex of the project, page 22.

Now, let's compare a different situation. There might be some potential clients which may already have a hot water tank integrated with renewable technologies, and might think of the possibility of switching to the presented PCM tank solution. The next table compares the case of acquiring the TESSE2B system versus staying with the hot water tank:

PCM tank vs Water tank, both 48 kWh capacity					
n° of Solar Collectors	Net Energy Stored (kWh)	Electricity Price (€/kWh)	Savings per year (€)	Price of the Tank (€)	Payback Period (years)
2	300,995	0,15	45,149	3000	66,446
3	591,703	0,15	88,755	3000	33,800
4	670,578	0,15	100,586	3000	29,825
5	602,146	0,15	90,322	3000	33,214
6	574,199	0,15	86,129	3000	34,831
7	589,352	0,15	88,402	3000	33,935
8	594,53	0,15	89,179	3000	33,640
9	609,998	0,15	91,499	3000	32,786

Table 9.3.3. Economic Analysis. Case: buying a PCM tank having before a hot water tank

Obviously, the payback period becomes larger. Surprisingly, the case in which switching to PCM seems to have more impact is when there are 4 solar collectors, being the payback period about 29 years. Note that the return on investment is high due to the high initial cost, but its worth mentioning that it would suppose saving around 100 € per year, which is still reasonable.

9.4. Environmental analysis

In terms of environmental impact, it must be said that while it seems to be positive, results may differ depending on the case. The electrical mix may be very different depending on the country, but also the impact will be bigger or smaller depending on the usage of the storage system. If a lot of energy is stored and used from the tanks, then the impact will be more positive.

The following calculations assess the CO₂ that will not be emitted by generating electricity from the grid, assuming that this energy is gathered from renewable sources in the PCM tank. However, this report does not assess the impact which has the manufacture of the PCM tank and its materials. Anyway, a extensive study should be carried out to evaluate the environmental impact on such processes, which could then be compared with the manufacture of a hot water tank, or other storage systems such as a lithium battery.

For this case, as the demosite is located in Calonge de Segarra, the electrical mix considered is the one from Spain. Data taken from annual reports by Red Eléctrica Española led to the following calculations:

	2016	2017
Electricity Demand (GWh)	265.009	268505
CO ₂ emmited (kg)	63,5 x 10 ⁹	74,8 x 10 ⁹
kg CO ₂ / kWh	0,2396	0,2785

Mean kg CO ₂ / kWh	0,2591
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Table 9.4.1. Spanish CO₂ emissions related to electricity generation

9. Economical and Environmental Analysis

9.4. Environmental analysis

After knowing the average CO₂ that is emitted when generating electricity, it is possible to estimate the savings in terms of CO₂ emissions that the TESSE²B solution can provide:

PCM tank, 48 kWh capacity

n° of Solar Collectors	Energy Stored Used (kWh)	CO2 savings (kg/year)
2	508,671	131,795
3	1107,083	286,841
4	1680,096	435,307
5	2086,537	540,615
6	2392,121	619,791
7	2618,148	678,354
8	2789,722	722,808
9	2917,724	755,973

PCM tank, 64 kWh capacity

n° of Solar Collectors	Energy Stored Used (kWh)	CO2 savings (kg/year)
2	508,671	131,795
3	1111,195	287,907
4	1699,510	440,337
5	2098,031	543,593
6	2420,695	627,194
7	2648,192	686,138
8	2817,764	730,074
9	2950,745	764,529

PCM tank, 80 kWh capacity

n° of Solar Collectors	Energy Stored Used (kWh)	CO2 savings (kg/year)
2	508,671	131,795
3	1111,195	287,907
4	1707,394	442,380
5	2104,886	545,369
6	2432,329	630,209
7	2665,094	690,517
8	2829,355	733,077
9	2963,698	767,885

Tables 9.4.2. CO₂ savings related to the usage of the TESSE²B solution as the main energy storage system

As expected, savings become higher when the PCM is associated with a bigger renewable installation.

Finally, it also arose the possibility to compare the PCM tanks with lithium batteries concerning the environmental impact. However, apparently there are no studies yet comparing these two technologies in terms of Lyfe Cycle Assessment, so it is an aspect yet to be investigated.

After saying that, it would be very interesting to deploy an LCA study to compare these two options in the near future.

10. Conclusions

In this study, the possibility of integrating a storage system using phase change materials has been tested in order to determine its feasibility and profitability. In first place, it is noticeable that the storage system always has to work in parallel with renewable technologies.

The given case is a pilot which includes solar thermal panels as well as borehole heat exchangers, which use geothermal energy along with a heat pump. Depending on the climate conditions, the type of dwelling and the energy demand, the PCM tank can be sized to cover daily demand or seasonal storage if needed. The TESSe2B project's demo site has a demand which has been found to be clearly concentrated in heating during winter.

The calculations indicate that the whole system can save more than 80% of the energy which nowadays the majority of families take from the grid to be used for heating, cooling, and domestic hot water. Besides representing a considerable reduction in the energy bill, as in the present days, the electricity from the grid is not "clean", applying renewable technologies along with thermal storage can have very positive impacts for the environment, as it contributes to reduce the levels of CO₂ emissions.

If renewable technologies to produce heat have to be installed at the house, the investment becomes much higher and, as a consequence, so does the payback period. However, the TESSe2B solution can also be adapted to any existing installation. On the other hand, after analyzing the economical aspects regarding the PCM storage system, the results indicate that the potential market will be for those cases in which there's a need to install

a storage system for the first time. TESSe²B solution is definitely better than a conventional water tank, but its differences are not remarkable, and so, the storage system might not attract users which already have a storage system paired with renewable technologies, and think of the possibility of switching to a PCM tank. Nonetheless, if eventually the conventional system stops working, and it is needed to be renovated, acquiring the TESSe2B solution would definitely improve the whole system efficiency.

In conclusion, when comparing the conventional use of a hot water tank to store heat against the use of a PCM tank, the results show that it is a more efficient system, as the heat losses are reduced due to the fact that is using latent heat, not sensible heat, and therefore it does not increase the temperature of the tank, what would make it prone to higher heat losses due to the large difference between the ambient temperature and the temperature inside the tank. This phenomena is more present in hot water tanks.

This leads to being able to use more energy from the storage tank when adopting the TESSe2B solution. In some cases, even if the price of the PCM tank is higher than the one of a water tank (same storage capacity), the payback period has been found to be lower.

Finally, as the PCM tank does not need as much volume as a water tank, it makes it a much more attractive alternative, as it can be easily integrated inside a house, as it doesn't take as much space, where it will always be more accessible and under better security conditions.

Bibliography

Books & scientific reports

- [1] Calvin W, C. Douglas Auburg. Electric water heater standby losses: comparison of conservation strategies and their energy savings. Bonneville Power Administration. 1984.
https://aceee.org/files/proceedings/1984/data/papers/SS84_Panel5_Paper_06.pdf
- [2] Camporeale, Patricia. Czajkowski, Jorge. Mercader Moyano, Pilar. Heating and cooling demand in buildings. Book of Proceedings of the 3rd International Congress on Sustainable Construction and Eco-Efficient Solutions.
- [3] Código Técnico de la Edificación (CTE). Documento Básico de Ahorro de Energía (DB-HE). March 2016.
- [4] Código Técnico de la Edificación (CTE). Documento Básico de la Salubridad (DB-HS). December 2017.
- [5] Creus Solé, Antonio. Energía Geotérmica de Baja Temperatura. Cano Pina, 2008.
- [6] Creus Solé, Antonio. Energías Renovables. Cano Pina, 2009.
- [7] Entranze Project. Heating and cooling energy demand and loads for building types in different countries of the EU. End-use Efficiency Research Group, Politecnico di Milano. March 2014:
http://www.entranze.eu/files/downloads/D2_3/Heating_and_cooling_energy_deman_and_loads_for_building_types_in_different_countries_of_the_EU.pdf
- [8] European Commission, Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions: An EU Strategy on Heating and Cooling, Brussels 16.2.2016.
- [9] Fan, Jianhua. Furbo, Simon. Thermal stratification in a hot water tank established by heat loss from the tank. Sciverse Science Direct. Elsevier, August 2012.
- [10] Li, Xiangli. Tong, Cang. Duanmu, Lin. Liu, Liangkan. Research on U-tube heat exchanger with shape-stabilized phase change backfill material. ScienceDirect, Procedia Engineering 146, 2016.
- [11] Manuel, Andreu. Diseño y Mantenimiento de una Instalación Solar Térmica, curso de formación superior. EducaciOnline. Eureka Media, 2009.
- [12] Peña Rodríguez, G. Peña Quintero, J.Y. Gómez Tovar, M.A. Determinación Experimental de la Conductividad Térmica Efectiva en Bloques Extinguidos de Arcilla Roja. Ciencia en Desarrollo, Vol. 5, pp-15-20. January-June 2014.
- [13] Red Eléctrica Española (REE). Publicaciones. Informe del Sistema Eléctrico Español 2017:
http://www.ree.es/sites/default/files/downloadable/avance_informe_sistema_electrico_2017_v3.pdf
- [14] Red Eléctrica Española (REE). Publicaciones. Informe del Sistema Eléctrico Español. Mayo 2018:
http://www.ree.es/sites/default/files/11_PUBLICACIONES/Documentos/ree-mayo-2018.pdf

Websites

- [15] AEMET. Atlas Climático Ibérico:
http://www.aemet.es/documentos/es/conocermas/recursos_en_linea/publicaciones_y_estudios/publicaciones/Atlas-climatologico/Atlas.pdf
- [16] Diario Renovables. Generación Eléctrica en España en 2017. January 2018:
<https://www.diariorenovables.com/2018/01/generacion-electrica-espana-2017-bajan.html>
- [17] Enter Shop. Hot Water Storage Tank catalogue:
<http://www.enter-shop.com.au/catalogue/c4/c163/p874>
- [18] Eurostat. Consumption of energy. June 2017:
http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Consumption_of_energy
- [19] Eurostat. Energy consumption and use by households. March 2017:
<http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/-/DDN-20170328-1>
- [20] Hutch. Product Catalogue 2017:
https://huch.com/fileadmin/user_upload/downloads/productcatalogue2017.pdf
- [21] IDAE. Atlas Eólico. <http://atlaseolico.idae.es/meteosim/>
- [22] Instituto Geológico y Minero de España (IGME). Mapa de la Zona 3000:
<http://info.igme.es/cartografiadigital/geologica/geodezona.aspx?intranet=false&Id=Z3000#mapas>
- [23] Instituto Geológico y Minero de España (IGME). Mapa Geológico:
<http://igme.maps.arcgis.com/home/webmap/viewer.html?webmap=44df600f5c6241b59edb596f54388ae4>
- [24] Instituto Geológico y Minero de España (IGME). Visor Cartográfico:
<http://info.igme.es/visorweb/>
- [25] Instituto Nacional de Estadística (INE). Datos climáticos:
<http://www.ine.es/jaxi/Datos.htm?path=/t38/p604/a2000/10/&file=1900001.px>
- [26] TESSE2B. The Smart Energy Storage. <http://tesse2b.eu>
- [27] XE Currency converter: <https://www.xe.com/currencyconverter/convert>
- [28] 1st Choice Hot water. Water Tank catalogue:
<https://1stchoicehotwater.com.au/product-category/hot-water-systems/domestic/electric-storage/>

